

Attenuating Masquerader Data Theft Attack In The Cloud

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Abstract—*Traditional data security techniques such as encryption of data have failed to prevent the data theft attack by an insider on the cloud premises. To prevent such attacks, we propose Fog Computing that will blur the attacker’s vision and hide the data. We achieve this by using together two techniques: user behaviour profiling and decoy document. User behaviour profiling means monitoring the user’s access pattern on the cloud and detect abnormal access decoy is a document used to confuse the attacker with bogus information. Thus, damage to data due to insider attack can be reduced.*

Keywords- Fog computing; decoy; user behavior profiling

I. INTRODUCTION (HEADING 1)

Cloud computing is Internet-based computing, where shared resources, software and information are provided to computers and other devices on-demand. It is a general term for anything that involves delivering hosted services over the Internet.

Cloud computing is gaining popularity as it provides different types of services like IaaS, PaaS, SaaS that too on different deployment models like private cloud, public cloud, hybrid cloud and community cloud. Cloud computing facilitates virtualization of resources like storage, processing, and compute. Migrating to cloud seems attractive because it relieves its users from installing and upgrading of hardware and software at user sites. It eliminates a major IT infrastructure investment and provides the system users access data and system from anywhere in the world. Pay only for use policy which otherwise would have been more expensive had the consumer did it manually on his local system is another reason. But security is a major concern when online storage of data comes into picture. For both providers and consumers it is a major challenge to overcome and withstand respectively. This problem aggregates when the storage is migrated on a cloud premises.

In this paper we will focus on storage as a service (part of IaaS) and enhance its security by employing fog computing.

II. BACKGROUND

A. Existing System Limitations

Cloud users have to register themselves with the cloud provider before they can access the cloud services. Registered users obtain username and password for authentication in order to access cloud infrastructure. User files are stored on cloud in encrypted format. But if an attacker obtains the username and password of a legitimate account and logs in with the corresponding credentials, he can access sensitive data of the legitimate user, thereby breaching all security measures.

B. Proposed

Fog computing is an approach to overcome this limitation to a great extent. It is the technology to launch disinformation attacks against malicious insiders, preventing them from distinguishing the real sensitive customer data from fake worthless data. The name ‘fog’ is used for two reasons: fog lies between users and cloud; fog blurs the vision of user and thus data behind fog remains hidden.

Interception of legitimate user’s data is prevented by encrypted data transmission and fog computing is used

to

- overcome masquerader attack, an attack where the attacker masks itself with the identity of a legitimate user
- minimize the damage due to data theft on cloud by decreasing the sensitivity of user information

III. APPROACH

Insider data theft attack is characterized by an attacker, who obtains the login credentials of a legitimate user and logs into the cloud using those credentials, for malicious purposes like stealing the legitimate user's data, etc. The two techniques: User behavior profiling and decoy document generation are discussed below. If used individually, they will provide partial detection of masquerade activity. But combination of user behavior profiling and decoy documents characterized in fog will help in baiting the insider data theft on cloud significantly.

A. User Behavior Profiling

A cloud user has some typical behavior of their own when they are accessing cloud services. This may be preferences, file naming, search pattern, session duration, types of operation etc. Moreover, a user remembers the file name that is uploaded, its location and contents. Seldom does

it happen that user forgets it. As a result, legitimate user exhibits a narrow search while looking for a particular file stored on their file space.

However, an attacker may be unaware or partially aware of the file and its contents. Therefore, they will exhibit a wide search pattern in search of user's sensitive data to steal. This is because the attacker may have to open every file to check its contents rapidly, navigates through all directories, etc. to find the data of their interest.

Second parameter which is used to learn user behavior is users mouse activities. Here we collect users real behavior data. This data contain following information. Mouse clicks per user session.i.e number of right clicks and left clicks, average distance traveled by mouse per session

Along with above parameters we can collect session time, login time, mac address information for creating user profile Whenever a user account is created, a user model is developed to record the user's behavior. This model populated every time a user session takes place. The user behavior is monitored during the session and compared with the earlier patterns. If deviation above a threshold is found, it is considered as a potential attack. When the user is new, possibilities of deviation from the user model is more because the model is in learning phase. Until sufficient training data is gathered, such deviations are frequent. But such deviations should not be considered as attack but should be treated as just another training data entry that will enhance the model to avoid false positives in future.

False positive is when the system suspects an attack even when it is not. The proposed system aims at reducing this rate.

B. Decoy Documents

These are documents placed on the user file space and shown to mislead/confuse the attacker. They pretend to contain sensitive information about the user. The decoy can be

- pre-generated and placed in user file space in advance or
- generated and shown to user in real time if a user activity seems suspicious

The pre-generated decoy may contain false sensitive information like login credentials, bank account details, which provokes the attacker to search for more such files. The decoy file names are kept enticing to trap the attacker

e.g Decoy Examples

For generation of decoy there are two parts: text decoy and image decoy.

Image Decoy:

For generation of image decoy on demand, we can change the properties of image so as to make it unidentifiable and insensitive. This insensitive image defeats the purpose of the attacker. For example, we can increase the sharpness of image to make it unidentifiable, in this way we can convert the sensitive image into

insensitive one by sharpening the image.

Fig.1 Decoy image generated from original image

Text Decoy:
For making the sensitive text insensitive useless text file

Original File:

this is a sample text file.
read by java program and print its contents.
suman is its author.
see sam if you find cant find jerry some different chisel contents

Decoy File:

this is extremely necessary. if a fruit was bought by her. sampler textfile. read by java program it was a sunny day and they played in garden. print its is contains confidential contents. suman is good at work. author likes to dance. see below sam if you find my dog cant find jerry some different. chisel likes coconuts contents

fig.2 Decoy text file

C. Combination of User behavior profiling and decoy generation

Both user behavior profiling and decoy generation method work hand in hand to provide a stronger mechanism to detect masquerade activity. Combination of the results obtained from the individual modules is shown in the given matrix.

	Normal Search Behaviour	Abnormal Search Behaviour
Decoy Clicked	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Legitimate user accidentally opens decoy Mimicry attack by masquerader 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Potential Attack
Decoy Not Clicked	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Safe access by legitimate user Unsafe access by traitor 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> New behaviour pattern by legitimate user New user

Fig.3 Matrix showing conclusions drawn from combination of user's search behavior and decoy document

D. Conceptual Architecture

A user logs into the cloud via a web browser on installed on a user device that is connected to Internet. In the proposed system, we insert a component called ‘fog’ between the user and cloud. As discussed above, fog is used to blur the attacker’s vision and hide the legitimate user’s sensitive data. Whenever the user requests a file, already stored on the cloud, for viewing or downloading, the user has to pass through the fog to reach the cloud. The fog is invisible to the user and incorporates security mechanism that user must pass in order to access original files.

Inside the fog, there is a sub-component called ‘user behavior profiling’ where algorithms are run to observe and analyze the logged in user’s activity and find out its deviation from the corresponding user model. If deviation is above a threshold, the user activity is labelled as suspicious otherwise normal. If normal, user is allowed to access the cloud and the requested (original) file is provided to them.

In case of suspicious, the user’s access to cloud is forbidden, and decoy files are shown to the user, instead of original file, in response to the user’s file request. The decoy files, when accessed, send beacons/alarming signal to the administrator who takes measures to safeguard user account.

Thus in the event of threat, sensitive data of the user is protected from potential attacker.

Fig.4 Conceptual architecture of the proposed system: fog hides the sensitive user data from the attacker and shows decoys to potential attack

IV. CONCLUSION

Cryptography techniques fail to protect user data in the event of insider attack or masquerader attack. Because security and privacy of user data are critical non-functional requirement of any cloud storage system, mechanisms must exist to prevent illegitimate access to sensitive data. With the help proposed model we can:

- Detect a masquerader on cloud
- Track masquerader activity on cloud

Alert the legitimate user and the administrator of threats encounter

Integration of bio-metric sensors viz. finger print scanner, retina scanner etc. can further increase the security by strengthening user authenticity procedure.

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